

Title: Stuff In A Box

ROBIN FOSTER, BATH SPA UNIVERSITY, UK

JOHN BOWERS, INDEPENDENT ARTIST-RESEARCHER, UK

1. PROGRAM NOTES

Stuff In A Box is a duo performance of hybrid rummaging. Rummaging is a practice where junk is manipulated with the hands to create a kind of acoustic noise music. Hybrid rummaging adds multiple forms of audio synthesis to the mix so that physical objects, body parts and electronic sound can all collide as equals.

We use bit-mask and cellular automata derived techniques, pulsar synthesis, scanned synthesis, adaptive room feedback, and live sampled wavetables, amongst other resources - all running on embedded devices and influenced by data from physical sensors as well as the touch of our hands.

The rummaging box containing the found junk becomes an interface, a complex tactile arena for interaction, and a staging for multiple materialities to collide. In this way, we demonstrate a characteristically brutal understanding of NIME 2024's conference theme, 'tactility in a hybrid world'.

Stuff In A Box is receiving its world premiere at NIME.

Fig. 1. Stuff in a box.

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). Copyright remains with the author(s).

DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/0000000.0000000>

Music Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression

NIME'24, 4–6 September, 2024, Utrecht, The Netherlands

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Our performance derives from our ongoing research into ‘hybrid-rummaging’; exploring how the physical performance practice of rummaging can be hybridised through digital technology.

Rummaging is a practice centred around using the hands and a box of found objects to make noise (see [1] and [2] for more details). Our hybrid-rummaging expands this practice, seeking to explore how rummaging as a paradigm might be applied at every level of our performance ecology.

We work with a range of technologies, from RFID, Bluetooth and video-tracking to tilt switches, electromagnetism and raw voltages, investigating how rummaging might be interfaced with these technologies, and the ways in which the technologies themselves might be appropriated, plundered and rummaged.

We believe our practice enables us to speak to fundamental issues in NIME and explore them in performance, matters such as the relationships between gesture and sound, different forms of materiality, and the sense we can give to concepts such as ‘interface’, ‘instrument’ and ‘expression’. Our approach to hybridism differs from many approaches that can be found in NIME. We do not translate one form of materiality into another. We do not get different materials or actions on them to relate via abstraction or representation. Rather, we treat all objects at the same level, a truly flat ontology in which things, our hands included, collide. Our work is, in some respects, a boundary condition for NIME research and performance that we hope will provoke reflection on these and other affairs: it’s all stuff in a box.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

The artists will submit their synthesis techniques and provide Front Of House with a stereo pair output from our onstage mixer (over balanced TRS or XLR).

We will supply all equipment needed for our electronic sounds. We will scavenge junk objects for rummaging on-site in Utrecht.

We request a pair of overhead microphones and stands to reinforce the acoustic sound of rummaging the objects and to balance that with the electronics. We prefer large diaphragm condenser microphones with a cardioid sensitivity to control feedback.

Our performance will require a table approximately 1.5m square and mains power.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

We provide the following as Supplementary Material.

- Video: StuffInABox.mp4 (564.3Mb)
- Audio: StuffInABox.aiff (27.1Mb)

ETHICAL STANDARDS

This work was conducted independently supported by the artists themselves. We have no financial or other conflicts of interest to report. The only human participants in the research that this proposal is based on are ourselves. Throughout we have ensured that the work has been done safely and with mutual consent. For example, while our work can involve the direct touch of electronic circuits, these are always low power, battery operated, and buffered from any mains powered equipment.

REFERENCES

- [1] John M Bowers, John Richards, Tim Shaw, Robin Foster, and Akihiro Kubota. 2023. Raw Data, Rough Mix: Towards an Integrated Practice of Making, Performance and Pedagogy. *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*. Mexico City, Mexico, pp.417–427. http://nime.org/proceedings/2023/nime2023_58.pdf
- [2] <https://robinfoster.net/> Visited 7th May 2024.